

CARBONIZED ELECTROSPUN LIGNIN FIBERS: PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Electrospun fibers of organosolv hardwood lignin (HL) were produced from solution blends of lignin and poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), and lignin and cellulose acetate (CA) blends. The fibers were thermostabilized and then carbonized at two different temperatures: 800 °C and 1000 (or 1100) °C. The results showed that carbonization temperature had a positive effect on reducing the final fiber diameter for HL/PEO blends but did not have a significant effect on the HL/CA fiber diameter. Raman spectroscopy of the fibers showed that HL/PEO fibers carbonized at higher temperatures had a higher percentage of graphitic structure with more alignments compared to other fibers. The results will help the selection of appropriate thermal conditions for carbonization of lignin fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers have a molecular structure containing more than 90 wt% carbon. The specific alignment and orientation of sheets of carbon (graphite) result in unique properties such as high mechanical properties (tensile strength in the range of 2 to 7 GPa; up to 3 GPa compression strength; tensile modulus of 200 to 900 GPa), good heat resistance, and high thermal and electrical conductivities [1]. Carbon fiber composites are highly sought-after in applications which require light weight and high-performance structural properties such as in the automotive and aerospace industries [2, 3]. Besides mechanical strength, carbon fibers also have good electrical and thermal conductivities which make them good candidates for applications in electronic devices. However, the application of carbon fibers has been limited due to the high material and processing costs of the precursors. Currently, industrial carbon fibers are mainly produced from polyacrylonitrile (PAN) with a smaller percentage produced from mesophase pitch [1]. PAN is a petroleum-based polymer that is synthesized and spun in a solution process. To be converted into carbon fibers, PAN requires a very slow heating process for carbonization which extends the processing time [1, 4].

In the move towards more sustainable and biobased materials, lignin is considered as a potential low cost and renewable resource-based candidate to replace PAN for some of the carbon fiber applications. Lignin is a highly available and low-cost coproduct of the cellulosic ethanol and paper industries. Currently, it has limited low-value applications and research is ongoing to produce more valuable products. Lignin has about 68 wt% carbon which is comparable to PAN but has a higher carbon yield and faster carbonization process compared to PAN [4].

In carbon fiber production, the first stage is spinning of the precursor material. Melt spinning and electrospinning of lignin have been studied [4]. Lignin has a low molecular weight and a broad molecular weight distribution. Therefore even at high concentrations of lignin, the chain entanglements are not enough to spin continuous smooth fibers. One way to improve the network of chain entanglements is blending of lignin with a second high molecular weight polymer [5-8]. Additionally, some researchers have studied the fractionation of lignin in order to extract higher molecular weight fractions which can be melt spun [4].

Electrospinning has been used as a simple technology to produce continuous submicron diameter fibers from a wide range of materials. Randomly oriented or aligned fiber mats can be produced by this method. Furthermore, it is convenient to incorporate nanoparticles in the fibers by simply dispersing the particles in the spinning solution. The fibers can be carbonized and the high surface area and porosity of the fibers are advantageous for applications of the carbonized fibers as anode, cathode, or separator materials in batteries or capacitors. The shear forces applied to the electrospinning jet acts to improve the molecular alignment which can improve the graphitization and conductivity properties of the resultant carbon fibers.

In the literature, electrospinning of kraft, soda, and organosolv lignin [3, 9], its blends with poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) [5, 7, 10-13], polyacrylonitrile (PAN) [6, 14-16], poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) [8, 17-19], chitosan [20], cellulose acetate [21], and soy protein [22] have been reported. Two major challenges for the electrospinning and carbonization of lignin-based fibers are the utilization of organic solvents in the polymer solution and percentage of polymer(s) blended with the lignin. Since most of the polymers have a low carbon yield, increasing the percentage of blending polymer may result in increasing the porosity of the fibers surface after carbonization. A high amount of porosity leads to lower mechanical strength of the fibers.

In this paper, electrospinning of aqueous lignin solutions blended with i) PEO and ii) cellulose acetate (CA) and the production of the carbonized fibers from them are reported. Iodine treatment of the lignin/CA fibers was used to improve and speed up the thermostabilization stage.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Organosolv hardwood lignin ($M_w = 1551.7$ g/mol) was provided by Lignol Innovations Ltd. (British Columbia, Canada). Cellulose acetate (CA) ($M_n \sim 30,000$ g/mol), poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) ($M_v = 2,000,000$ g/mol) and acetone were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) and sodium hydroxide were purchased from Fisher Scientific. Iodine crystals were purchased from The Nichols Chemical Company, Limited.

2.2 Electrospinning of fibers

In order to prepare the electrospinning solutions, lignin and the blending polymer were completely dissolved in the solvent separately and then appropriate amount of each solution were mixed to get the final lignin blend solution. Final solution composition and total concentration were selected based on the types of polymers and the solution spinnability. The solution formulations are presented in Table 1. For electrospinning, a NANON-01A electrospinning setup with a stationary plate collector (MECC Co., Ltd. Japan) was used. The voltage, feed rate, distance between needle and collector, and other spinning parameters were adjusted to obtain a continuous spinning [21, 23].

Blending polymer	Solvent	Lignin to blending polymer ratio	Total polymer concentration (wt%)	Reference
PEO	Sodium hydroxide solution (0.5 N)	19/1	7	[23]
CA	Acetone/DMAc: 2/1	2/1	30	[21]

Table 1: Electrospinning solution compositions.

2.3 Iodine treatment of fibers

The electrospun HL/CA fibers were wrapped around a rectangular metal frame and placed in a glass jar containing iodine crystals and sealed. The jar was kept in an oven at 100 °C for different time lengths between 1 to 24 h. The vials were cooled to room temperature before the fibers were removed [21].

2.4 Carbonization

Carbonization of the fibers was performed in two steps. First, in the thermostabilization step, fibers were slowly heated in air to induce polymer crosslinking. The crosslinking acts to increase the thermal transition points of the polymers or completely remove them. The second step was carbonization. In this step, the material was heated in nitrogen to a high temperature to carbonize. Table 2 summarizes the heating conditions used for each fiber. Thermal treatments were performed in a Carbolite 1200 °C G-range horizontal tube furnace.

Fiber composition	Thermostabilization			Carbonization			Reference
	Heating rate (°C/min)	Maximum temperature (°C)	Residence time at Max. T (h)	Heating rate (°C/min)	Maximum temperature (°C)	Residence time at Max. T (h)	
HL/CA	2	300	2	2	800 1000	1	[21]
HL/PEO	0.5	250	2	2	800 1100	3	---

Table 2: Thermal conditions for carbonization.

2.5 Characterization

The morphology of the fibers was studied with a FEI–Inspect S50 scanning electron microscope (SEM). The average fiber diameter was calculated from at least 40 measurements using the ImageJ software. Elemental analysis of the materials was performed using an X-Max 20 energy dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS) from Oxford Instruments.

Raman spectroscopy was performed with a 785 nm near-infrared laser (Renishaw Raman spectrometer). The power was set to 50%. Raman peaks were analysed by fitting Lorentzian curves.

Thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis was used to study the thermal stability of the fibers. Fibers were heated in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min to 800 °C.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Different polymer ratios were tested to find the best ratio to spin smooth fibers without beading. SEM results (Fig. 1) showed that lignin to CA ratios of 1/1, 2/1, and 4/1 created smooth fibers without beading [21]. For HL/PEO samples, the lignin content could be increased to 19 times more than PEO; meaning 95 wt% of the fiber composition was lignin. This increase in lignin content is possible due to strong interactions between lignin and PEO in alkaline solution. However, the strong viscoelastic forces resist the elongational stretching of the electrospinning solution jet and average fiber diameter increased compared to HL/CA fibers. The average diameter of the fibers is presented in Table 3.

The effect of iodine absorption on thermal treatment of lignin/CA fibers was studied. The amount of iodine absorption on the lignin and CA powders were determined at different iodination times. Lignin has much higher iodine absorption capacity compared to CA. With an increase in the iodination time and therefore higher amount of iodine absorbed, the thermal degradation of lignin powder started at higher temperatures. In addition, the residue after carbonization also increased until it reached a relatively constant amount. For CA, short iodination times did not have a significant effect on the thermal stability but 4 h iodination time caused CA to completely degrade during TGA experiment at 800 °C. Iodination also helped the lignin powder to retain its shape during thermal treatment. This

treatment showed slight improvements in the carbon content of the carbonized material [21]. The results showed that for the blend fibers, increased iodination time after 1 h caused melting and fusion of the fibers during the treatment. Since the fibers have smaller diameters and a high surface area compared to particles, the rate of iodine absorption is higher for the fibers. Therefore, even at shorter time the same yield was obtained. A treatment time of 20 min was selected to reach a balance between iodination and preservation of the fiber morphology [21].

Fiber blends of HL/CA with a 2/1 ratio which had been iodinated for 20 min were studied for thermostabilization and carbonization. Iodinated fibers had a better preservation of morphology after thermostabilization and also after carbonization they retained their flexible fibrous structure. SEM images of carbonized fibers are shown in Fig. 1. HL/PEO fibers carbonized at 800 °C had a rough surface compared to fibers carbonized at 1100 °C. The EDS results showed a higher percentage of sodium in the rough areas. Therefore, the roughness can be due to melting and recrystallization of excess of sodium in the fibers.

The average diameter of HL/CA fibers was reduced to about 200 – 300 nm after carbonization (Table 3). The final diameter did not show a dependence on the carbonization temperature or the initial diameter [21]. For HL/PEO fibers, higher temperatures resulted in a greater decrease in fiber diameter. The carbon content of the final fibers reached more than 90 %. Analysis of the fibers by FTIR showed complete removal of functional groups after carbonization.

Figure 1: SEM images of electrospun fibers before and after carbonization, a) HL/CA: 2/1 from Ref. [21], b) HL/PEO: 19/1, c) HL/CA carbonized at 800 °C from Ref. [21], d) HL/CA carbonized at 1000 °C from Ref. [21], e) HL/PEO carbonized at 800 °C, f) HL/CA carbonized at 1100 °C.

Fiber composition	As-spun fiber diameter (nm)	Carbonized fiber diameter (nm) [carbonization T]	Percentage reduction (%)	Ref.
HL/CA	450 ± 100	250 ± 50 [1000 °C]	44	[21]
HL/PEO	2930 ± 600	2224 ± 654 [800 °C] 640 ± 82 [1100 °C]	24 78	---

Table 3: Average fiber diameters before and after carbonization.

Thermal stability of HL/PEO fibers was studied by TGA (Fig. 2). The thermal stability of the thermostabilized fibers is almost the same as the as-spun fibers with a final residue of ~ 40%. These fibers have two-step degradation. The first degradation happens at around 337 °C which is close to the degradation of PEO and HL powders. The second step occurs at about 750 °C. Carbonized fibers produced by heating the fibers at a heating rate of 7 °C/min to 800 °C and held for 3 h were also tested by TGA. As expected, these fibers had a higher thermal stability and a final residue of 66%. The carbonized fibers have about 10% weight loss at 100 °C which is due to volatiles and absorbed moisture. The other two weight losses at 545 and 777 °C are due to incomplete carbonization of the fibers.

Figure 2: Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) results for HL/PEO fibers, thermostabilized fibers, and carbonized fibers at 800 °C, a) TGA, b) derivative TGA.

Raman spectra of the samples provided information regarding their carbon structure (Fig. 3). The D peak with a center at around 1360 cm^{-1} is due to sp^3 disordered bonds. The G band with a center at 1580 cm^{-1} is due to in-plane sp^2 graphitic bonds. The ratio of D peak height to G peak height which is also shown as $R=I(D) / I(G)$ shows the alignment of the graphitic section and also degree of graphitization. Lower amounts of R shows the more sp^2 carbons [24]. The results are shown in Table 4. The peak positions for HL/PEO fibers are lower than HL/CA fibers. The R values are lower for fibers carbonized at higher temperatures and also for HL/PEO fibers compared to HL/CA fibers. The graphitic mole fraction, x_G , has the opposite trend and is higher for HL/PEO carbonized at higher temperatures. The x_G shows that a higher degree of graphitization and better alignment of graphitic planes was obtained for HL/PEO fibers carbonized at a higher temperature.

Figure 3: Raman spectra of HL/PEO fibers carbonized at 1100 °C and deconvoluted peaks.

Sample (carbonization T)	D peak position (cm ⁻¹)	G peak position (cm ⁻¹)	R = I(D) / I(G)	$x_G = I(G)/(I(D) + I(G))$	Ref.
HL/CA (800 °C)	1318	1585	3.89	0.205	[21]
HL/CA (1000 °C)	1301	1585	3.51	0.222	[21]
HL/PEO (800 °C)	1308	1588	2.03	0.329	---
HL/PEO (1100 °C)	1294	1591	1.93	0.341	---

Table 4: D and G peak positions, R ratio, and fraction of graphitic structure for carbonized HL composite fibers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Electrospun fibers were produced from solution blends of hardwood lignin and PEO in alkaline solvents, and lignin and CA in organic solvents. The results showed that the weight percentage of lignin in HL/PEO fibers could be increased to 95 wt% of fibers but for CA the maximum content which resulted in smooth fibers was HL/CA: 4/1 which is 80 wt% of the final fibers. The diameter of HL/PEO fibers were about 3 μm and were reduced to sub-micron diameters after carbonization. Reduction in diameter was dependent on the carbonization temperature. CA blend fibers had diameters of about 500 nm which reduced to 200 – 300 nm after carbonization for both carbonization temperatures tested. Raman spectroscopy results showed HL/PEO fibers carbonized at higher temperatures had the highest graphitic mole fraction and better alignment of graphitic planes compared to HL/PEO carbonized at lower temperature and HL/CA. The results provide information for selecting suitable thermal conditions for carbonization and also show the effect of blending polymer on the processing and final properties of the carbonized fibers. The fibers have potential applications in batteries and energy storage devices, as well as being used as absorbents in filtration applications.

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